

THE ENGINEERING PROPERTIES OF CORAL LIMESTONE USED AS SUB BASE IN DAR-BAGAMOYO ROAD PROJECT

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents and discusses the unusual poor engineering properties of coral limestone from Mpiji Borrow area in Bagamoyo District - Tanzania used as subbase materials during the construction of Wazo Hill – Bagamoyo Road. The discussion is based on the study and assessment of road subbase made of coral limestone at the project site in the coast of Dar Es Salaam and Coastal region, which involved about 148,000 square metres of pavement from chainage 28+900 to 42+800. The road length is 42.8 Kilometres starting at Wazo Hill Junction (Chainage 0+000) ending at Bagamoyo town (Chainage 42+800). The deterioration and damage of pavement started while the road construction was ongoing. The pavement failure warranted an immediate forensic investigation to establish the probable cause of the pavement failure. The geoforensic investigation established that the primary cause of pavement failure was due to softening and swelling of coralline subbase caused by the imbibition of water supplied to the subbase layer during crushed base placing and compaction using 'slushing' compaction procedures.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

As a result of the significant formation of potholes in the flexible pavement from Km 28+900 - 42+800 on the Dar Es Salaam – Bagamoyo road, a forensic investigation was undertaken. It was established beyond all reasonable doubt that the cause of failure was the coralline material used as a subbase. Thus, the study was confined mainly to assess the used subbase coral limestone's properties. The sub-base material in question was sourced from Mpiji borrow area, which was among the eight borrow areas indicated in the project Materials Report as a potential source of subbase materials. Much of the cracking and potholes formation resulted within the rainy season of October – December 2000, about 2-

3 months after covering the subbase with crushed stone base and priming. This paper discusses the damage investigation, firstly, the scope of the investigation followed by the pavement subbase characteristic. With these data, the performance of the coralline subbase geo-materials as they affected the pavement is evaluated.

2.0 SCOPE OF INVESTIGATION

The forensic investigation conducted in 2001 consisted of reviewing available project documents, a visual inspection of the damaged area, and laboratory testing. Bulk soil samples were taken from the failed sections along the road and Mpiji borrow-pit for laboratory testing. It is to be observed that the Mpiji subbase material placed on the failed sections along the road was blended with 25% of natural sand to reduce the plasticity index and to improve the bearing capacity before laying. The tests carried out on subbase soil samples consisted of modified and standard proctor tests, un-soaked and soaked CBR test, Atterberg limits, in-place moisture content tests, in-place soil density determination, grain size analysis, X-Ray Diffraction tests and CBR-swell index.

3.0 PAVEMENT STRUCTURE

The pavement thickness was 550 mm, comprising 150 mm of a high quality crushed granitic-gneiss stone base, 200 mm of natural gravel coral subbase [*soaked CBR more than 30*] and 200 mm of topping material [*soaked CBR of more than 15*]. The subgrade below the topping material consisted of sandy clay or silty/clayey sand with a minimum CBR value of 7. The pavement design called for the double surface dressing of 20 mm + 10 mm. The pavement structure was designed following the standard procedures given in the Overseas Road Note 31, capable of enduring traffic loading of T2 [*0.3-0.7 million equivalent*

standard axes] for the design period of 20 years.

3.1 PAVEMENT CONSTRUCTION METHODOLOGY

Before pavement construction, the roadbed and topping layer material was compacted to the desired degree of compaction given in the project specifications. The sand-blended coralline subbase layer was placed on top of the approved topping layer.

The project specifications called for moisture content during compaction to be within the range of $OMC \pm 2\%$. The construction record indicated that the compaction of coralline subbase geomaterial was carried out in most cases on the dry side of the optimum moisture content, i.e. within the range of $OMC - 2\%$ to $OMC - 1\%$. The crushed stone base compaction was carried out using a compaction procedure commonly referred to as "slushing". This compaction procedure requires excessive use of water.

4.0 LABORATORY RESULTS

4.1 GEOTECHNICAL PROPERTIES OF SUBBASE GEOMATERIAL

The physical properties of the coral material were tested before placing and found to comply with project specifications. The compaction specification for the subbase soil called for minimum compaction of 98% of AASHTO T180. The designer projected that if the coralline subbase can be compacted as specified, it should meet the highway carriageway's long-term performance needs.

During construction, care was taken to ensure that the subbase was constructed according to the designated specifications and standard. Consequently, laboratory and field density tests were performed regularly to verify that the compaction and other physical properties were met. As the sub-base placing progressed, localised failure in the form of potholes was observed during the rainy season of October – December of the year 2000.

4.2 CLAY MINERALOGY

The mineralogical analysis was performed on the soil samples from Mpji borrow-pit. It was established that the geomaterial contains calcite as primary composition, microline, albite, anorthilite and sanidine in small proportional. Calcite is one of the weakest minerals, which on Mohs scale of hardness is ranked as number 3; thus, prone to breakdown under repeated traffic loading.

X-Ray Diffraction analysis [XRD] was carried out to determine the type of clay minerals within the geomaterial. It was established that the Mpji borrow area geomaterial contains expansive clay mineral smectite (montmorillonite). The XRD performed on the particles passing 0.063 mm revealed that the Mpji borrow material has a significant amount of smectite ranging from 60%-70% [3]. If this is converted to represent the whole soil mass, then the percentage of smectite in this coralline subbase material ranged from 3.80%-4.40%.

Smectite mineral is known for its enormous volume change potential. This is attributed to the large breadth-to-thickness ratio in excess of 100 and specific surface area as much as $800 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ [1]. Because of their surface areas and adsorptive properties, a significant volume change (shrink/swell) and softening can occur due to moisture change. Even in small quantities in the soil as low as 2%, smectite clay has been reported to cause instability to a 5m embankment [7]. When dry, the smectite bearing soils are hard and stable. When placed below optimum moisture content and exposed to infiltration/groundwater inflow, the clay's bonding capacity is lost, and the soil fill strength becomes very low and unstable material.

4.3 GRADING

The summary of grading test results shown in Figure 1, 2 and 3 indicate that the coralline subbase geomaterial was undergoing mechanical breakdown under repeated traffic loading from construction and normal traffic. The grading of the geomaterial after trafficking was found to be finer than before trafficking. The in-situ mechanical breakdown of the

coralline subbase materials can be associated with the softness of the calcite mineral within the subbase soils.

Figure 1: Grading before and after trafficking (Percentage passing 4.75 mm sieve)

Figure 2: Grading before and after trafficking (percentage passing 0.075 mm sieve size)

Figure 3: average grading before and after trafficking

Since contact forces in soil element increase with particle size and the probability of a defect in a given particle increase with its size, the potential for particle breakage increased as the particle size increased.

4.4 SOIL PLASTICITY

Several samples were taken from the borrow pit and tested for the plasticity index in "as dug state". The Atterberg limit tests on this coralline material yielded a liquid limit ranging from 23-43%, and the plasticity index varied from 12-17%. The summary of the plasticity data of the 'as dug' borrow material, blended geomaterial (before trafficking), and after trafficking (blended) is shown in Figure 4 and 5. The plasticity plot indicates that most soil samples from the borrow area, in "as dug state", are plotting within the montmorillonite band. The plasticity plot supports the XRD test results, which revealed that the coralline geomaterial contains an expansive montmorillonite clay mineral within the soil matrix.

After blending the geomaterial with 25% of cohesionless sand, the geomaterial plots within the band of illitic clay on the plasticity chart. The plasticity plot suggests that blending the geomaterial transformed the geomaterial mineralogical composition, making the illite the main clay composition within the soil matrix. The plasticity index of the blended geomaterial ranged from 7-12, while the liquid limit ranged from 23-28. Therefore, the plasticity index of the geomaterial before placing was less than 12.

The plasticity of the soil samples taken from the failed sections of the road exhibited an increase in the plasticity index. It is hypothesised that the increase in the plasticity index was due to the crushing of the overly soft calcite particles, which led to the production of plastic fine from montmorillonite bearing soil particles. Since the fine generated originated from montmorillonite bearing rock, the plasticity test results of the soil samples taken from the failed road sections are plotting within the band of the montmorillonite clay.

Figure 4: plot of the geomaterial on the plasticity chart [2]

Figure 5: Plasticity index before and after trafficking (blended geomaterial)

The geomaterial with a liquid limit of less than 50 and a plasticity index of less than 25 usually are classified as low swelling potential geomaterial. Therefore, the coralline geomaterial used as a subbase can be classified as low swelling potential geomaterial based on the plasticity data.

4.5 COMPACTION PROPERTIES

Six standard [AASHTO T99] and six modified [AASHTO T180] maximum dry density curves were developed. The AASHTO T180 compaction was carried out for three soil samples taken from Mpiji borrow area (unblended geomaterial) and the remaining three from the failed section of the road (blended geomaterial). The subbase soils sampled from the failed section road had

maximum dry density ranging from 2132 kg/m³ to 2175 kg/m³ with optimum water content ranging from 6.4% to 6.8%, with an average of 6.6%. For the samples taken from the borrow area (unblended material), the maximum dry density ranged from 2095-2110 kg/m³ suggesting that blending the subbase soil with sand improved the grading of the geomaterial resulting in an increase of the maximum dry density.

A comparison between the modified and standard curves indicates that a modified (AASHTO T180) compared to standard compaction effort (AASHTO T99) increased the soil maximum dry density by about 5.3% and decreased the optimum moisture content by about 2%. The summary of the test results is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: maximum dry density and optimum moisture content

4.6 CALIFORNIA BEARING RATIO (CBR) TESTING

A total of 134 California Bearing Ratio (CBR) tests were performed in the soaked and unsoaked conditions.

Figure 7 show the CBR test results for the blended geomaterial tested before trafficking and after trafficking. It can be seen that the coralline subbase geomaterial was placed with a soaked CBR of more than 30, which was the minimum CBR value specified in the project specification. However, after trafficking, some of the tested soil samples from the failed road sections exhibited a soaked CBR value of less

than 30. It is postulated that the decrease of CBR value after trafficking was due to in situ degradation and mechanical breakdown of the overly soft coralline geomaterial leading to the generation of the additional plastic fine within the soil matrix, which drastically decreased the CBR value.

Figure 7: CBR before and after trafficking

4.6.1 SOAKED CBR PROPERTIES

CBR test results were run on soil sampled from the borrow area (unblended) and the failed road sections (blended). The soaked CBR test results for borrow area geomaterials (unblended) compacted at varying compaction effort are shown in Figure 8 and 9, from which it can be seen that the coralline geomaterial is extremely sensitive to moulding moisture content. The specified CBR value of more than 30 can be achieved only when the geomaterial is compacted to at least 98% within a narrow range of moisture content of about 1.3% (OMC-0.8% and OMC+0.5%). Beyond this moisture content range, the geomaterial exhibited an egregious drop in CBR value. It is observed that the geomaterial showed considerable instability when moulding moisture content deviated from the optimum moisture content. When the soil was compacted at $\pm 2\%$ on either side of the optimum moisture content, the CBR value egregiously dropped from the peak value to a CBR value of about 10. This trend was observed at all level of compaction ranging from 95-101%.

Figure 10 shows the CBR values at the diverse range of compaction and moisture content for the sand-blended geomaterial sampled from the failed sections along the road. It can be seen that the CBR of the blended geomaterial

is higher than that of unblended material sampled from the borrow area. The moisture sensitivity of the blended geomaterial improved slightly compared to the unblended borrow area geomaterial. For the blended geomaterial to meet the project specifications, the geomaterial compaction was supposed to be carried out within the moisture range of 2.2%, i.e., OMC -1.3% and OMC+0.7%. Despite the improvement in moisture sensitivity after blending with sand, the compaction range of moisture content is very narrow, suggesting that the coralline geomaterial was still extremely sensitive to moulding moisture content even after blending with sand.

Figure 8: soaked CBR of borrow area geomaterial (unblended)

Figure 11 shows a series of CBR test results to simulate the CBR value at OMC and OMC-2% for the sand-blended geomaterials taken from the failed road section. The CBR at OMC simulates the geomaterial CBR values reported from the laboratory as part of routine testing. The soaked CBR value determination at OMC-2% simulates the in-situ CBR after the imbibition of water. The test results indicate that out of 62 soil samples compacted at OMC-2% moisture content, only eight soil samples meet the project specification. Seven soil samples met the project specifications marginally. Some soil samples were compacted at OMC-2% up to 103% of the maximum dry density, yet they failed to meet the prerequisite CBR value of 30.

Figure 9: soaked Iso-CBR for borrow area geomaterial (unblended)

Figure 10: soaked CBR values for the blended material sampled from the failed section

The soaked CBR test results shown in Figure 11 and 12 indicate that if the geomaterial moulding moisture content deviates from the optimum moisture content by $\pm 2\%$, the geomaterial fails to meet the project specification regardless of the applied compaction effort.

Figure 11: Soaked CBR value at compacted at OMC and OMC-2% (blended geomaterial from failed road sections)

Figure 12: The soaked CBR value for blended geomaterial taken from the failed sections

4.6.2 UNSOAKED CBR PROPERTIES

The CBR values in the unsoaked state represent the state of soil immediately after placing.

Figures 13 and 14 shows the CBR values at diverse moisture content and compaction for the unblended geomaterial taken from the borrow area. In contrast, Figure 15 shows the CBR and moisture data for blended geomaterial sampled from failed road sections.

For all tests on the un-soaked unblended soil samples taken from the borrow area, high CBR values between 75 to 170 were obtained when the coralline subbase material was compacted on the dry side of optimum moisture content. The blended soil samples taken from the failed road section showed a higher unsoaked CBR value in the range of 105 to 210 when compacted on the dry side of the optimum moisture content.

Soil samples compacted at the wet side near optimum moisture began a catastrophic drop in strength. They resulted in negligible CBR value compared to the dry side by the time this coralline material reaches moisture wet of optimum, i.e., OMC + 2%. This trend is demonstrated in all samples tested across a range of moisture content from dry to wet.

Figure 15 shows unsoaked CBR test results for the sand blended geomaterial sampled from the failed road section from which it can be inferred that immediately after placing the compacted coralline geomaterial was having a CBR value of about 100 when compacted a minimum value of 98% at field placing moisture content of OMC-2%. However, it can be seen that the geomaterial can only maintain the CBR value of more than 30 when the moisture content is less than 7.2% (0.2% higher than optimum moisture content).

From Figures 13, 14 and 15, it can be seen that the bearing capacity of the coralline geomaterial improved by the increase in compaction effort when the geomaterial is compacted on the dry side of the optimum moisture content. However, an increase in compaction effort is not associated with an increase in CBR values once the moulding moisture content of the geomaterial exceeds the optimum moisture content. In other words, it can be stated that beyond OMC+1% moisture content, the CBR of the geomaterial is almost the same regardless of the applied compaction energy. Furthermore, it can be seen that the strength obtained from mechanical compactions were largely destroyed when the d compacted coralline subbase was exposed to water

The reduction of soil bearing capacity reported in Figure 13, 14 and 15 are based on the

laboratory test results. During construction, the strength reduction will be even more severe than observed in the laboratory since in the field, a free swell will be experienced. In contrast, in the laboratory, a free swell is not achieved because the compaction mould restricts it.

Figure 13: unsoaked CBR for the geomaterial from the borrow area

Figure 14: Iso-CBR values (unsoaked) for borrow geomaterial

Figure 15: The unsoaked CBR value for the geomaterial from the failed road section

4.6.3 SWELL CHARACTERISTIC

Figure 16 shows the CBR swell index of the geomaterial before and after trafficking. Before trafficking, the CBR swell index was less than 0.5%. The CBR swell index of some soil samples taken from the failed section along the alignment exhibited a higher CBR swell index of more than 0.5%. It is postulated that the increase in CBR swell index was due to an increase in plastic fine content generated from the breakdown of montmorillonite bearing rock during trafficking.

Figure 16: CBR-swell index before and after trafficking

Figure 17 and 18 shows the CBR swell index at diverse compaction and moisture content. As expected, the soil compacted at low moisture content on the dry side of the optimum moisture content shows a large amount of swell with percent swell decreasing with increasing moulding moisture content. The

project specification called for a maximum CBR swell index of 0.5% determined from the CBR compacted at optimum moisture content to 98% of the maximum dry density of modified AASHTO. It can be seen that the CBR swell index at optimum moisture content meets the project specifications even at low compaction effort of 95%. The departure of the compaction moisture content from the optimum moisture content to the dry side of the optimum moisture content is associated with an exponential increase in CBR swell index.

Figure 17: CBR swell index at diverse moisture and degree of compaction

A series of CBR swell index tests was carried out at OMC and OMC-2% at diverse compaction effort using geomaterial sampled from the failed section along the road. The CBR swell index at OMC simulates the laboratory reported test results as part of routine testing. The CBR swell index at OMC-2% simulates the expected field swelling condition. The test results indicate that the CBR swell indices increased when the compaction effort was reduced. At a compaction effort of more than 102%, the CBR swell at OMC and OMC-2 is almost the same. However, at a compaction degree of less than 100%, an increase in swell CBR index for the geomaterial tested at OMC-2% was noted. The summary of the CBR swell index at OMC and OMC-2% is shown in Figure 19, from which it can be seen that at OMC (97% compaction), the expected CBR swell index is estimated to be 0.4%, while at OMC-2%, the expected CBR swell index is 0.75% (88%

increase in CBR swell index). It is worth mentioning that this measured CBR swell index is a restrained CBR swell index, not a free swell.

Figure 18: CBR swell index at diverse moisture and degree of compaction, sample from failed road section

Figure 19: CBR swell index at OMC and OMC-2% for a sample from the failed section

There is no international recognised threshold for the soil to be classified as expansive soil based on the CBR swell index. The Tanzania Standard Specification allows the maximum CBR swell index of 2% for the geomaterial to be used for fill. Therefore, based on this specification, it is reasonable to state that soil can be classified as expansive when the CBR swell index is more than 2%. Consequently, based on the CBR swell index test results of

the coralline geomaterial, the soil cannot be classified as expansive.

Although the geomaterial was found to contain an expansive clay mineral smectite in the coralline subbase soil, the CBR swell indices of less than the specified value of 0.5% were recorded when the geomaterial was compacted at optimum moisture content. Furthermore, the recorded plasticity index of less than 12% makes the geomaterial to be not susceptible to be classified as expansive.

Therefore, based on both CBR swell index and plasticity index test results, the coralline subbase was classified as low swelling potential geomaterial based on the laboratory test results. However, in the field, the geomaterial showed a high degree of instability after imbibing water. As part of the geo-forensic investigation, a site performance trial was carried out to simulate the coralline subbase geomaterial performance in a saturated state. The trial was carried out at Km 30+150-30+175 and Km 30+100-30+125 using subbase material blended with 40% of the screened natural river sand from Mpji. It is worth mentioning that the failed geomaterial placed as a subbase layer was blended with 25% of natural sand. The trial section was brought to OMC prior to rolling and compacted to average relative compaction of 99.7% for the section of Km 30+150-30+175 and 99.5% for the section of Km 30+100-30+125. Both sections passed the proof rolling test, which was carried out using a water bowser with 15,000 m³ of water. Thereafter, the sub-base material was sprinkled with water to saturation using a water bowser, and the density retested. It was found that the relative compaction drastically decreased to 95.6% (4.1% drop) and 95.0% (4.5% drop) while the moisture content averaged to 10.1% from 6.1% (an increase of 4%). After saturation, the coralline geomaterial was proof-rolled again, and severe pumping was observed, signifying that the strength of the coralline subbase material was substantially reduced to a level that it was impossible to support the loading imposed on it. Reduction in density is a typical characteristic of the smectite bearing swelling soil. When soaked, the soil tends to absorb a large amount of water, leading to an increase in the gross volume of material. Thus, soil density and bearing capacity dramatically

reduced. Using dry density data before swelling (at OMC) and after swelling, the percentage of swelling can be computed, which was found to be 4.3% (for the first section) and 4.7% (for the second section) as opposed to CBR swell index value of less than 0.5% measured from the laboratory CBR-swell test. The actual computed swell results suggest that the laboratory CBR swell index test does not realistically depict the swell in the field since the sample in CBR is restrained from swelling by compaction mould. The actual in-situ swell was found to more than nine times the value measured using the CBR swell index test because the subbase layer was not restrained from swelling; thus, actual free swell was achieved. The percentage of swelling after saturation was computed using the expression given in equation 1, where p_d is the dry density before swelling and p_{swell} is the dry density after swelling.

$$p_{swell} = \frac{p_d}{1 + \%Swell} \dots \dots (1)$$

The trial section carried out to simulate the wet condition indicated that the material used as subbase material is expansive even though the standard procedures of identifying soil expansivity failed to classify the geomaterial as expansive. It is observed that even blending the geomaterial with a high sand content of up to 40%, the expansivity potential of the blended geomaterial was still controlled mainly by the presence of montmorillonite clay within the soil matrix.

The coralline subbase geomaterial, when compacted at optimum moisture content or on the dry side of optimum moisture content, assumed a soil structure conducive to high strength and stiffness. However, this structure allowed appreciable swell with exposure to water. The swell is disruptive and remoulds the soil and separates the soil particles to the extent that a large fraction of the initial strength was lost after water imbibition.

From the field performance trial, it can be seen that without specifically testing the swell and softening effect in the field, the swell and softening potential of the coralline subbase soil from Mpiji could remain unsuspected because

of a low plasticity index and low CBR-swell index value recorded in the laboratory.

5.0 IN-SITU MOISTURE CONTENT

The in-situ moisture content of the failed subbase sections was determined. The test results as given in Figure 20 indicates that the subbase geomaterial, in most cases, was saturated with moisture content above the optimum moisture content suggesting that the coralline subbase material imbibed water after placement. The water was supplied to the subbase layer during compaction of the crushed base using a compaction procedure commonly known as 'slushing'. This crushed base compaction method requires a copious amount of water to achieve a high degree of interlock within the crushed stone matrix and tightly knit the aggregates particles.

The increase in moisture content above optimum moisture content causes positive pore water pressure to develop under rapidly applied loads that reduce the effective stress and, therefore, the pavement deformation resistance of the geomaterial. Since the stiffness of the geomaterial is the measure of the load spreading-ability of the geomaterial, the softened subbase experienced higher stress from the traffic leading to an increase in strain and accumulation of plastic strain.

Figure 20: in-situ moisture content of the geomaterial

5.1 PREDICTION OF IN SITU CBR

The best-known engineering tool for estimating the in situ CBR of the pavement layers is DCP. Unfortunately, DCP was not available during this investigation. Therefore, the in-situ CBR was predicted based on the relationship between moisture content and unsoaked CBR shown in Figure 15, which depicts the state of geomaterial immediately after placing. Since the minimum specified field compaction was 98%, a moisture content-CBR relationship curve at 99%, as given in Figure 15, is selected for predicting the in situ CBR values at various moulding/placing moisture content. The Moisture and CBR data were fitted using the mathematical function shown in Equation 2, from which the in-situ CBR value at diverse moisture content can be computed. The computed in situ CBR of the coralline geomaterial is shown in Figure 22. It can be seen that only 9 out of 38 tested locations whose in situ CBR value is estimated to be more than the specified value of 30.

$$CBR = -112.9 \tanh(0.3062MC - 1.41) + 108.6 \dots \text{Eqn}(2)$$

Where,
MC is moisture content in %

During placement of crushed stone base, the slushing compaction procedures of stone base supplied sufficient amount of water to the underlying coralline subbase layer leading to softening and weakening of the upper 100 mm subbase layer leading to egregious drop pf CBR value from about 100 immediately after placing to about 10 after imbibition of water. The uppermost layer of the subbase was found to have higher moisture content, while the lower 100 mm subbase was found to be relatively dry and stable.

Figure 21: Model for estimating the in-situ CBR of the geomaterial.

Figure 22: location and estimated in-situ CBR

6.0 DISTRESS MECHANISM

Structural deterioration under traffic takes place in every road pavement, although in a well-designed and well-constructed one; its development is very slow and seasonal. Under load, the stress condition in the crushed base is analogous to those of the loaded beam. Due to bending, the base is subjected to compression at the top and tension at the bottom. The cohesion-less base material that makes the base has little tensile strength and generally depend on subbase/subgrade to provide lateral restraint. Due to the development of an overly soft transitional subbase layer, very little restraint was provided, leading to loss of support and

integrity with subsequent cracking and formation of potholes which were mainly confined at the pavement edge due to stress concentration immediately under the surface. Due to significant deformation in the subbase layer, the base layer underwent bending due to differences in the modular ratio of the geomaterial. The distress mechanism and potholing formation model is shown in Figure 23.

Figure 23: Potholes forming model due to loss of support

6.1. MODELLING PAVEMENT RESPONSE

The pavement response on loading was checked by computing the vertical compressive strain at the top of the subbase layer using MEPADS software. The analysis of pavement response was carried out by taking standard loading of a dual tire of 20 kN and tire pressure of 650 kPa. The pavement material resilient modulus proposed in South African mechanistic pavement design [11] is used to compute the pavement response. The resilient modulus used is shown in Table 3 and 4.

Table 3: Resilient modulus of the pavement material (contract design)

Material	CBR value	Resilient modulus
Crushed Base	>100	350 MPa
Granular sub base	>30	150 MPa
Topping	>15	120 MPa
Subgrade	>7	70 MPa

When the subbase geomaterial was exposed to water, the subbase was transformed into two layers, i.e., the soaked and weak uppermost top layer with CBR as low as 10. At the same time, the remaining half maintained the CBR value of at least 30. Therefore, after placing, the pavement structure can be

modelled with two layers of the subbase. The estimated resilient modulus of the geomaterial after imbibing water and softening is shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Resilient modulus of the pavement material (after softening)

Material	CBR value	Resilient modulus
Crushed Base	>100	350 MPa
Granular sub base	>10	70 MPa
Granular sub base	>30	150 MPa
Topping	>15	120 MPa
Subgrade	>7	70 MPa

Figure 24 shows the computed vertical compressive strain at the top of the subbase layer. It can be seen that at the interface of the base and subbase, the compressive strain increased due to a change of material stiffness, leading to an increase of compressive strain. The increase in vertical compressive strain is more marked at the interface of the softened subbase layer. The computed compressive strain using subbase as per design is 1060 microstrain, while after softening, the computed compressive strain is 1570 (48% increase). The computed vertical compressive strain using MEPads software is given in Figure 24.

After saturation of the subbase layer, the base geomaterial was overlain by soft and weak subbase with low stiffness. The modular ratio between the crushed stone base and the softened underlying subbase per design is estimated to be $350/150=2.3$. After softening, the modular ratio is estimated to be $350/70=5$. When the ratio of unbound layer E_1 to that of unbound underlying layer E_{i+1} is $E_1/E_{i+1} > 2.5$, the horizontal tensile strain will develop at the bottom of the underlying layer [6]. Under traffic loading, the overlying layer de-compact until such time that the stiffness of the layer is reduced to the limiting value at which tensile stresses will not develop. Therefore, the stiffness of the crushed layer was progressively reduced since the base layer was forced to bend excessively to support the traffic loading.

Figure 24: Computed vertical compressive strain

7.0 CONCLUSIONS

The project soil discussed in this paper is coral limestone from Mpiji along the coast of Dar Es Salaam - Tanzania. The coralline geomaterials was used as subbase material from chainage 28+900 – 42+800 designed to support a traffic category of T2 (0.3-0.7 Million ESA).

When the coralline subbase soils were tested across the typical recommended and specified compaction and moisture ranges of $OMC \pm 2\%$, this coralline subbase gravel was found to be extremely detrimental for pavement support and construction. From unsoaked and soaked CBR testing, it was found that this soil had egregious sensitivity to moisture content. If compacted dry of optimum at high densities, the coralline soil will appear sufficiently stable to pass the proof rolling but become egregiously unstable after imbibing water due to the presence of montmorillonite clay mineral within the soil matrix. Deviation of placing moisture content from optimum moisture content was found to have a very devastating effect on the bearing strength of the coralline soil and resulted in a drastic drop in CBR value.

The increase in moisture content in the coralline subbase geomaterial during compaction of crushed stone base led the smectite-bearing coralline geomaterial to expand, soften, decrease in density and

decrease in CBR value, ultimately leading to loss of integrity and support. Thus, the formation of potholes was due to the inexorable intrinsic and extrinsic nature of the coralline material used as a subbase material. Swelling is normally associated with mobilisation of swelling pressure and swelling strain which contributed to the formation of cracks and subsequently formation of potholes. The pavement is intolerant of this expansion and/or shrinkage; ultimately, the movement produced cracks that developed into potholes. The degree of failure varied from place to place due to spatial moisture distribution within the pavement

For the coralline geomaterial tested during this investigation, it was established that estimation of swelling potential based on the CBR swell index could be deceiving due to the fact in the compaction mould, the soil is restrained while the field the material is not restrained; thus, a free swell is achieved. The test results presented herein indicate that the field swell can be as much as nine times more than the CBR swell index measured in the laboratory. Therefore, the CBR swell index should not be considered as a free swell potential of the soil expected in the field at any dry density and moisture but an indication of the swell. Similarly, classification of potential to swell using plasticity index can be equally deceiving for some geomaterials. Based on the traditional method of evaluating the geomaterial swell using plasticity index and CBR swell index, the coralline geomaterial can be classified as non-expansive. However, through full-scale trial sections, the geomaterial was found to be expansive.

The primary cause of pavement distress and failure was primarily due to the expansion and softening of sub-base geomaterial, which is a characteristic property of project coralline geomaterial that contains expansive smectite clay used as a subbase material.

The secondary cause of pavement distress was due to the use of overly soft coralline subbase geomaterial, which underwent in-situ mechanical breakdown producing additional plastic fine.

8.0 RECOMMENDATIONS

The main input for pavement thickness design is CBR. This implies that for the pavement to perform as expected, the CBR values assumed during pavement design for various pavement layers must be achieved in the field for the pavement to perform in accordance with the design. However, it is a custom practice to use the dry density of the compacted earthworks and pavement layers as the only means of ensuring that the pavement will perform in accordance with the design. The placement moisture content in most cases is ignored, and the approval of the pavement layers is granted once the pavement layers achieve the specified minimum compaction requirements. This study indicates that without testing the soil within the full range of moisture content specified during compaction, i.e., $OMC \pm 2\%$, to determine the CBR value, the dry field density is likely to give misleading results on the performance of the pavement, which may lead to premature failure of the pavement.

Most of the project specification calls for the CBR to be determined at optimum moisture content while the specified field moisture compaction is normally specified to be in the range of $OMC \pm 2\%$. The pavement design, in most cases, is based on the soaked CBR at optimum moisture content. However, some geomaterial like the coralline geomaterial tested during this investigation was found to be extremely sensitive to moulding moisture content. Therefore, to ascertain the performance of the geomaterial, the CBR testing needs to be carried out in a full range of the specified placement moisture content. The compaction of geomaterial shall not only be compacted to the specified density but also at a proper moisture content. For some geomaterial like the coralline subbase discussed herein, the placement moisture content of the geomaterial dictates the performance of the geomaterial. Based on this study, the following recommendations are made:

- To test the soil across the typically recommended or specified moisture and compaction ranges to ascertain the soil's critical behaviour prior to the approval of any proposed borrow area. Testing

through a typical specified compaction moisture range may allow relaxation or more strict control of moisture content in the field.

- To review the CML 1.10 and 1.11 Tanzania Testing procedures of CBR to include a clause explicitly to address the effect of moulding/placement moisture content on the strength of the soil. Similarly, article 3606(c) of Tanzania Standard Specification for Road Works 2000, which allows compaction on the dry side of optimum moisture content (75% of the Optimum moisture content) should be reviewed to allow compaction above optimum moisture since some soils are likely to show considerable instability when compacted at moisture content below optimum. Specifically, swelling clays should be compacted wet of the optimum in order to minimise swelling potential.
- This study has clearly demonstrated that the performance of some soil depends on the placement moisture content during compaction but not on achieved dry density.
- The use of crushed stone underlain with an unstabilised subbase is not permitted pursuant to clause 7.2.2 of the Tanzania pavement design manual. The granular subbase shall be overlain by crushed bases only and only when the granular subbase is tested and proved that increase in moisture content is not egregiously affecting the bearing capacity of the geomaterial.
- The CBR test results shall be performed such that the dry density and moisture content of the laboratory CBR specimen replicates the dry density and moisture content specified in the standard or special specification, i.e. when the specified compaction moisture content is 75% of the OMC, then the CBR shall be tested in the full range of moisture from 75% of OMC to OMC, if the specification calls for $OMC \pm 2\%$, then the CBR shall be tested in the full range of the specified moisture content of $OMC \pm 2\%$.
- Clause 3700 of Tanzania specifications call for the minimum Ten per cent fine for gravel geomaterial with CBR of more than 60 to be 50 kN. There is no particle strength specification for geomaterial with

CBR of less than 60. This study has established that if overly soft geomaterial is used as a subbase, they may undergo mechanical breakdown during trafficking leading to premature pavement distress due to the generation of the additional fine within the soil matrix.

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